

ISic1296

I.Sicily inscription 1296

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 260

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Μνησθοῖ
2. Ἐνκάρπιν
3. χρηστή καὶ
4. ἄμεμπτος
5. ἔζησεν ἔτη
6. ν΄

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

May Enkarpin be remembered, honest and blameless. Lived for 50 years.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492901

EDCS 39101666

PHI 140788

PHI 316304

Bibliography

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